

VALKYRIES

Map of Standards and joint roadmap

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1. Executive Summary

WP2 provides the design, specifications, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle. This includes an in-depth review of system requirements, outcomes from consultations with stakeholders, and pre-standardization research.

The Deliverable 2.4 *Map of Standards and joint roadmap* presents the analysis and map of the planned and ongoing VALKYRIES-related standardization actions, depicting a joint roadmap of them.

As part of WP2, Deliverable 2.4 will provide the pre-standardization research and harmonization and standardization strategies. This will guide the VALKYRIES engagement in the pre-standardization review, standardization actions, and requirements that need to be taken into account throughout the project life cycle.

The harmonization and standardization process is a multidisciplinary process where cross-sectoral experts with heterogeneous competence shall contribute, providing support in multiple initiatives, such as literature identification, evaluation and information exchange.

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

Both natural and man-made disasters are directly related with loss of human lives, severe socio-economic impacts, as well as impacts on the environment. Beyond the most frequent hazards, there are non-routine events that disrupt the normal functioning of a community or a society, causing widespread and overwhelming loss and impact.

As the world adopted more sophisticated technologies and became further industrialized, the occurrences and impacts of technological-driven disasters increased.

Crisis management implies networking and communication with all the stakeholders and the general public. Interoperability is critical, and a strong cross-sector, cross-border, and/or cross-hierarchy coordination is needed.

Recent studies such as the *EU Mandate M/487* revealed that the European Union is not yet at a stage where responders can interconnect information management systems to share situation assessments or automate coordinated response procedures.

Current searches and specific literature in emergency management have highlighted the importance of operational process gap identification and standardization.

Figure 1. Literature about standardization necessities.

Doc title: Map of Standards and joint roadmap

EU has evolved towards bringing strong capabilities for joint coordination and cross-sectoral cooperation between the Member States. As mentioned above, studies like the *EU Mandate M/487* to Establish EU Security Standards reveal significant open issues and gaps concerning the standardization and harmonization of common procedures focalized at semantic, planning, resilience, and organizational interoperability aspects, most of them being addressed from a holistic approach. Nevertheless, they integrate the needs of the local and Pan-European Emergency Medical Services at first responses, at the same time that weakly placing values on technological, procedural, collaborative and educational emerging opportunities arriving at the EU Security Market, which is highly fragmented and entails strong social implications.

As an example of those gaps, the organizational structures, and processes for disaster management differ considerably within the European Commission and among its Member States. Another important issue is the fact that due to differences between legal systems, there is no harmonized terminology and no formal or consistent EU-wide list that defines all disaster management tasks. Finally, regarding the disaster management market, the EC aims to establish a better functioning of the Internal European Market for these security technologies.

In parallel with the *EU Mandate M/487*, *Article 12 of the Decision No 1313/2013/EU* of the European Parliament and the Council states that *“The Commission shall encourage Member States to address, either individually or through a consortium of Member States cooperating together on common risks, any strategic capacity gaps that have been identified in accordance with paragraph 2 ⁽¹⁾. The Commission may support the Member States in those activities in accordance with Article 20, points (i) and (j) of Article 21(1) and Article 21(2).”*

“(1) Where potentially significant gaps have been identified, the Commission shall examine whether the necessary capacities are available to the Member States outside the European Response Coordinator Centre”

In line with these needs, the project VALKYRIES aims to analyse, improve and demonstrate infrastructures, protocols, and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during the deployment, intervention, and local/remote coordination of first aid responders in multi-victim disasters, including crowdsourcing and public alerting.

3.1. Cross-border Emergency Management Gaps

Crisis Management depends on the type of crisis only in the way different tools are used. The activity principles turned out to be the same for all crisis situations, therefore it would be possible to analyse different types of emergencies from the perspective of the first response coordination and communication.

Professional experience and emergency evaluations have identified common gaps between countries, that can affect the success of a cross-border and multi-victim disaster's first response. The aim of 3 of VALKYRIES project "Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation" is to research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines, and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardization actions.

Based on the *EU Mandate M/487*, previous researches, and European legislation, there are several gaps that were already identified as part of the VALKYRIES project Grant Agreement. All of them would be considered and evaluated over the standardization process.

1. Terminology and semantic interoperability.
2. Ethical, legal and societal aspects.
3. Technical interoperability and deployment.
4. Standards, including voluntary Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs).
5. Communication infrastructure.
6. Operational coordination technologies.
7. Reconnaissance, triage, and crisis response planning.
8. Maintenance, logistics, and deployment.
9. Command and control and support to operational decision-making.
10. Warning.
11. Education and training for first aid responses.
12. Social awareness.

4. Objectives

Deliverable 2.4 can serve as a reference document that will facilitate the experts work on gaps prioritization and identification of standardisation opportunities, beyond the work programs of the European, international and military organisations dedicated to this purpose. The main objective would be to develop a sustainable process in support of improving future standardisation.

The objectives defined for this delivery are:

- Provide a common reference point for discussions between experts about communication, equipment and resources.
- Extend the evaluation of the procedures with documented specifications.
- Improve interoperability, commonality, and compatibility between different regions.
- Formalise certification and quality control for continuing performance.

5. Map of Standards

In standardisation, it is paramount to find gaps and commonalities. In this direction, this section explains the procedure required to obtain the necessary information.

5.1 Design of collection data tools (formats)

First of all, data sort should be collected for each partner and source of information.

Secondary, a mapping of current standards should be performed. A data collection by the partners should be carried out as well.

To make the collection of standards and information handy, it must be harmonised. For this purpose, data collection formats are developed, which are filled in by the partners. These forms classify the information in order to make it easier to compare, to look for gaps and commonalities.

5.1.1 Legal standard Identification

This format collects information that affects the whole sector or the involved countries.

All the standards related to the project must be collected and all the standards that directly affects VALYRIES in the Use Cases (UC) must be collected too.

The information is sorted for every UCs and a common part with documents that are applicable for every UCs. This format could be filled out by all partners although each partner will provide more information on their native country. Nevertheless, any partner could add the documents and information that may affect the project.

There are some points on which information must be collected:

- National or international legislation.
- Standards.
- International agreements.
- Cross-border agreements.
- Institutional operational process.
- Training standard.
- Technology standards.
- Any other that may affect us.

In order to sorting the data, the template will have the following columns

- Who provides the information.
- The document reference.
- A brief introduction.
- Publication date.
- Country affected.
- Source (link).

(See Annex A: Legal standard Identification)

5.1.2 Pre-identification gaps and commonalities

This format collects pre-identified gaps and commonalities detected by partners. Some data, like gaps and commonalities, can be detected before the meetings with the partners. This is because there is experience, literature and previous projects about this gaps and commonalities.

Smaller-scale drills could be organised in different countries to detect gaps before the use cases.

Professional experience

The aim of this pre-identification of gaps is to detect issues or failures that affect members in an emergency. Based on this, project needs can be generated and scopes can be defined. This work will be useful to make future meetings more agile, quicker and efficient, as it focuses on real end-user problems.

On the other hand, the importance of partner's professional experience should be highlighted. This information is paramount in order to identify the different gaps, define the scope and set a goal during the project. The partners' experience in emergencies and their cross-border and cross-sectoral knowledge makes them identify gaps based on their own personal experience.

Literature and previous projects.

Gaps will not only be identified in the information collection by the partners.

There are previous literature and projects that have already identified gaps. This studied and verified information can be very helpful. In addition, this previous works can support our results.

For example, could be compiled reports from international organizations that have evaluated interventions of intervention teams in catastrophic situations.

(See Annex B: Pre-identification gaps)

5.1.3 Matrix tool

This format collects information concerning each emergency member.

Due to the cross-border nature of the project, a comparison between the countries of the Use Cases in different areas will be made. Therefore, there will be a matrix tool for each Use Case (UC).

This collection of information is essential since it is the fundamental pillar of the analysis of the partner's methodology in both parts of the border.

To make this comparison, the matrix tool will be used. For this reason, recorded and classified data will be compared.

There are different types of matching depending on the type of the data. The comparison will be different and the complexity of the data should be taken into account. It is not the same situation to compare:

Complex information. E.g. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)

There are necessary open-ended questions.

In its decision making, how does the country raise the emergency level?

Simple information. E.g. Vehicle equipment

There are necessary close-ended questions.

The vehicle carries a radio system? Yes/No.

As in other formats, partners must provide the necessary information for the comparison. Nevertheless, each partner will bring more information from their native country.

Some points on which information must be compared:

- Planning.
- Command & Control.
- First Responders.
- Emergency levels.
- Minimum equipment (vehicles)
- Communication.
- Training.

(See Annex C: Matrix UC1)

5.2 VALKYRIES' partners to share all the relevant information

Different meetings are scheduled with the partners to explain the information required and what is the scope. Plenary meetings and Use Cases meetings are used for asking and detecting relevant information. The most effective way to show partners the necessary information is to detect together information that should be added to the documents.

5.3 Gaps and Commonalities identification

This phase of harmonisation has not yet started, so it is complex to specify the procedure.

This phase may change according to project needs.

Once the common frame of reference has been provided with the information collected experts in each area will be brought together to discuss about this topic.

5.3.1 Workshops sessions preparation

First of all, a pre-session preparation should be carried out before the sessions:

- Check the information for every area.
- Sort the information for every area.
- Rule out areas outside the scope of the project, with the agreement of the leaders.

5.3.2 Workshops and expert's feedback

For these workshops, work will be carried out on the basis of the documents pre-identification of gaps and matrix

Once this information has been filtered, a second verification with experts, for example the external advisory board, will be carried out.

This point is really important as it will help us to focus on the problems that affect us most and define the scope of future session.

5.3.3 Final workshops

The final workshop will depend on the necessities of harmonisation, defining a high level harmonisation and a low level harmonisation.

- High level harmonisation:

Extended Delphi methodology, approach of Ulstein methodology.

This process requires more resources, but the output obtained will be complete and consensual. Participants need to be physically present or participate online but at the same time.

Only in this way they can discuss the issues.

- Low level harmonisation:

Delphi methodology.

This process requires less resources. It is quicker and it is not necessary for participants to schedule a meeting so that they can do it at different times and pool their results later.

This methodology will be used in areas where there is no major disagreement.

5.4 Suggestions and improvements

This phase of harmonisation has not yet started, so it is complex to specify the procedure.

This phase may change according to project needs.

5.4.1 Suggestions and improvement draft

The results obtained from the workshops will be shared with all VALKYRIES´ partners before being submitted for approval and include feedback.

5.4.2 Final Suggestions and improvement

The output of the project may vary greatly depending on how the following months and the sessions with partners develop.

It is intended that guidelines and suggested in each of the areas will provide a new framework for the continuous improvement of these areas.

5.4.3 Continuing improvement

This methodology will be used in areas where there is no major disagreement in order to Improve interoperability, commonality, and compatibility between different regions.

6 Joint Roadmap

Figure 2: European pre-standardization map and joint roadmap.

6.1 Road map justification

VALKYRIES project has a strong complexity as it is being developed by companies and researchers from different countries, with different expertise and professional skills, which may affect the project development and timeline

The main risks identified are:

- Document in different languages (e.g. legal documents, existent standardisation documents or SOP)
- Different terminology.
- Different expertise and emergency understanding.
- Experts representation, since it could be difficult to assure the involvement of a similar number of experts in each sector.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex A: Legal standard Identification

VALKYRIES

Legal Standard Identification

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Use Case	Partner	Contact person	Doc. Reference	Introduction/Scope	Publication date	Country/Region	Link
T7.5 -UC1: Spain-Portugal				Leader: Servicio de urgencias y emergencias de la comunidad de Madrid SUMMA112 (SMS)			
T7.6 -UC2: Slovakia-Austria				Leader: International Security and Emergency Management Institute (ISEMI)			
T7.7 -UC3: Bulgaria-Greece				Leader: Bulgarian Defense Institute (BDI)			
T7.8 -UC4: Norway- Netherlands- Denmark				Leader: University of South-Eastern Norway (USN)			
Common to all use cases							

7.2 Annex B: Pre-identification of gaps

VALKYRIES

Pre-identification of gaps

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WP3- Responsible innovation, certification and exploitation			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Operational procedures	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Ethical, legal and societal aspects	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Ethical, legal and societal aspects	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Interoperability	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Operational procedures	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Operational procedures	Other...Please add as many professional experience sections as you may need	Doc name:
Year:			
Link:			
Justification:			

Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency: Issue/gap: Summary of the situation:	
	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency: Issue/gap: Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name: Year: Link: Justification:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name: Year: Link: Justification:	

WP4-Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Communication infrastructure	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Justification:	

The digitalisation of first aid actuations	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Other...Please add as many professional experience sections as you may need	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
Link:			
Justification:			

WP5- Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses

Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Knowledge exchange and access	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Maintenance, logistics and Deployment	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Command and Control and support to operational decision-making	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	

Common Operational Picture and warning	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:		
		Issue/gap:		
		Summary of the situation:		
	Other...Please add as many professional experience sections as you may need		Doc name:	
Year:				
Link:				
Justification:				
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:		
		Issue/gap:		
		Summary of the situation:		
	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:		
		Issue/gap:		
		Summary of the situation:		
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"		Doc name:	
			Year:	
			Link:	
			Justification:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"		Doc name:	
			Year:	
Link:				
Justification:				

WP6- Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses			
Gaps identified	Type of input	Justification	Vakyrie's Partner
Resource Federation and trusted information sharing	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
Education and Training for first aid responses	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
Raising practitioner and social awareness	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	
Civil-Military Cooperation	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	

Civil Protection and Aid Volunteerism	Professional experience - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	
Others (please add as many gaps sections as you may need)	Professional experience- 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Professional experience - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Type of emergency:	
		Issue/gap:	
		Summary of the situation:	
	Literature - 1 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
		Link:	
		Justification:	
	Literature - 2 "Please add here the specific gap name"	Doc name:	
		Year:	
Link:			
Justification:			

7.3 Annex C: Matrix UC1

VALKYRIES

Matrix UC1

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TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisisresponse planning. Leader(TASS) T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)	
	Spain	Portugal
Planing		
INSTITUTION		
TERRITORIAL EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLAN		
HAZARD-SPECIFIC EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLAN		
INTEGRATION PLAN		
HAZARD MAPPING		
RESOURCES MAPPING		
PERMANENT COMMAND AND CONTROL FACILITIES		
ACTIVATION RESPONSABILITY		
ACTIVATION CRITERIA		
ACTIVATION PROCEDURE		
CATEGORIZATION CRITERIA		
ALERT AND WARNING PLAN		
EVALUATION PLAN(emergency levels)		
LOCKDOWN PLAN		
SHELTER-IN-PLACE PLAN		
EVACUATION PLAN		
SHELTERING PLAN		
OPERATIONAL PLAN		
TACTICAL PLAN		
DEMOBILIZATION CRITERIA		
DEMOBILIZATION PROCEDURE		
PLAN DISSEMINATION		
PLAN IMPLEMENTARION		
PLAN TRAINING		

PLAN MAITENANCE		
PLAN REVIEW		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making. Leader(ISEMI) Leader(TASS)	
Comand & Control	Spain	Portugal
INCIDENT COMMAND RESPONSABILITY		
INCIDENT COMMANDER		
LIAISON RESPONSABILITY		
COMMUNICATION RESPONSABILITY		
ALERT AND WARNING RESPONSABILITY		
SPECIAL TECHNICAL SUPPORT RESPONSABILITY		
SAFETY COMMAND		
OPERATIONS COMMAND		
LOGISTIC COMMAND		
MEDICAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE GLOBAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE FIREFIGHTERS COMMAND		
ON SCENE RESCUERS COMMAND		
ON SCENE SECURITY COMMAND		
ON SCENE FORENSIC COMMAND		
ON SCENE MEDICAL COMMAND		
ON SCENE LOGISTIC COMMAND		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET: **T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning. Leader(TASS)**

First Responders	Spain	Portugal
HAZARD CONTROL RESPONSABILITY		
DAMMAGE EVALUATION RESPONSABILITY		
ZONATION RESPONSABILITY		
ACCESS CONTROL RESPONSABILITY		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING RESPONSABILITY		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING COMMAND		
VEHICLES REGISTRATION AND TRACKING PROCEDURE		
RESCUE RESPONSABILITY		
RESCUE TRIAGE COMMAND		
RESCUE TRIAGE PROCEDURE		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING RESPONSABILITY		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING COMMAND		
VICTIMS REGISTRATION AND TRACKING PROCEDURE		
TREATMENT TRIAGE RESPONSABILITY		
TREATMENT TRIAGE COMMAND		
TREATMENT TRIAGE PROCEDURE		
STRETCHER TRANSPORT RESPONSABILITY		

STRETCHER TRANSPORT COMMAND		
STRETCHER TRANSPORT PROCEDURE		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE RESPONSABILITY		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE COMMAND		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE PROCEDURE		
ON SCENE HEALTH CARE FACILITIES		
EVACUATION TRIAGE RESPONSABILITY		
EVACUATION TRIAGE COMMAND		
EVACUATION TRIAGE PROCEDURE		
EVACUATION RESPONSABILITY		
EVACUATION COMMAND		
EVACUATION PROCEDURE		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		
T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisisresponse planning. Leader (TASS)		
T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning. Leader (TASS)		
T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)		
Emergency levels	Spain	Portugal
INSTITUTIONAL LEVEL		
LOCAL LEVEL		
REGIONAL LEVEL		
NATIONAL LEVEL		
NATIONAL LEVEL		
CROSS-NATIONAL LEVEL		
INTERNATIONAL LEVEL		
MILITARY LEVEL		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	T4.1 . First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units Leader(USN) T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment. Leader (AREU)	
Minimun equipment (Vehicles)	Spain	Portugal
FIREFIGHTERS VEHICLES		
FIREFIGHTERS PPE		
FIREFIGHTERS WEARABLES		
FIREFIGHTERS EVALUATION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS FORCES SIGNAGE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS HAZARD CONTROL EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS EXTINTION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS RESCUE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS ILUMINATION EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS CBRNE EQ		
FIREFIGHTERS COMM EQ		
SECURITY FORCES VEHICLES		
SECURITY FORCES PPE		
SECURITY FORCES WEARABLES		
SECURITY FORCES SIGNAGE EQ		
SECURITY FORCES COMM EQ		
EMS VEHICLES		
EMS PPE		
EMS WEARABLES		
EMS SIGNAGE EQ		
EMS TRIAGE EQ		
EMS MEDICAL CARE EQ		
EMS FACILITIES EQ		
EMS COMM EQ		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:	T4.2 Trusted Communication infrastructure and end-user terminals. Leader(UMU) T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment. Leader (AREU) T4.3 The digitalization on first aid actuations. Leader (INDRA)	
	Spain	Portugal
Communication		
FIREFIGHTERS COMMUNICATIONS		
RESCUERS COMMUNICATIONS		
SECURITY FORCES COMMUNICATIONS		
EMS COMMUNICATIONS		
MILITARY COMMUNICATIONS		
CIVIL PROTECTION COMMUNICATION		
RED CROSS COMMUNICATION		
OTHER INVOLVED RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS		
INTERINSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATIONS		
C&C COMMUNICATIONS		
CROSS-NATIONAL COMMUNICATIONS		

TASK INVOLVED IN THE MATRIX SHEET:		T6.2 Education and Training for first aid responses. Leader(BDI)	
Training	Spain	Portugal	
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER FIREFIGHTERS			
FIREFIGHTERS MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE			
FIREFIGHTERS ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING			
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER SECURITY FORCES			
SECURITY MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE			
SECURITY FORCES ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING			
VOLUNTEERS / CAREER EMS			
EMS MANDATORY OFFICIAL DEGREE			
EMS ADITIONAL MANDATORY TRAINNING			

7.4 Annex D: Glossary

Acronym	Description
WP	Advanced Command Post
UC	Use Case
SOPs	Standard Operational Procedures
C&C	Command and Control
EAB	External Advisory Board
EU	European Union
FAV	First Aid Vehicles
GA	Grant Agreement
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service
GIS	Geographic Information System
EMS	Emergency Medical Services
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCD	Minimum Common Data
MCDT1	MCD Primary Triage
MCDT2	MCD Secondary Triage